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Digital twin using nested machine learning for sintering deformation of ceramic-matrix composites

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The problem

Computer simulated sintering distortion of a CMC part using ABAQUS

A digital twin

Digital twin of sintering with nested ANN, that enables commercial finite element package to do machine learning

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Replace constitutive law with an ANN

A constitutive law (using Olevsky's model as an example)

A constitutive law in the format of an ANN

Implementation of ANN in Abaqus using CREEP subroutine

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SUBROUTINE CREEP (DECRA, DESWA, STATEV, SERD, EC, ESW, P, QTILD,  
1 TEMP, DTEMP, PREDEF, DPRED, TIME, DTIME, CMNAME, LEXIMP, LEND,  
2 COORDS, NSTATV, NOEL, NPT, LAYER, KSPT, KSTEP, KINC)  
  
C  
C INCLUDE 'ABA_PARAM.INC'  
C  
C CHARACTER*80 CMNAME  
C  
C DIMENSION DECRA (5), DESWA (5), STATEV (*), PREDEF (*), DPRED (*),  
1 TIME (2), EC (2), ESW (2), COORDS (*)  
C  
C user coding t  
C  
RETURN  
END
```


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Training the ANN

A constitutive law in the format of an ANN

Forward calculation

$$z_j^{lk} = f(z_0^{lk}) = f\left(\sum_i (w_{ji}^l z_i^{(l-1)k}) + b_j^l\right)$$

Approach 1 – standalone training

ANN → Training → Implement in FEA software

Approach 2 – training ANN nested in finite element analysis using a new backpropagation algorithm

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Application of DFEM in Sintering Distortion Analysis of Oxide-Oxide Ceramic Matrix Composite: Digital Twin, Baber Saleem, Ran He, Peter Polak, James Lander, Ian Edmonds, Xiaoxia Yu, Jingzhe Pan, 2025, accepted by International Journal of Ceramic Engineering and Science

**Our best effort for a CMC panel so far
– ongoing work**

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Conclusion:

We have developed digital twins with nested ANNs, which enables commercial finite element package to do machine learning.

The UK Research and Innovation Strength in Places Fund

The Midlands

Midlands advanced ceramics for industry 4.0 SIPF investment: £18 million

The Midlands Industrial Ceramics Group (MICG) is a consortium of researchers, manufacturers and end-users. Together, the group will develop streamlined processes for proving and bringing new advanced ceramics technologies to market faster, with less energy usage and lower carbon emissions. This will enable effective problem-solving and faster commercialisation of new products, unlocking improved performance for next generation products including:

- fuel cells and batteries
- 5G communications
- ceramic-matrix composites for aero engines
- medical devices.

It will also boost the competitiveness of manufacturers in the region by developing a robust advanced ceramics supply chain, able to export into one of the fastest growing international industry sub-sectors. Advanced ceramics are vital 'enablers' for many manufacturing sectors

Introducing Midlands Advanced Ceramics for Industry 4.0, the project that will help the Midlands' ceramics industry to innovate more efficiently. Video credit: UKRI. On-screen captions and an auto generated transcript is available on YouTube.

Vision

Our vision is to revolutionise ceramic manufacturing by enabling seamless, real-time interactions between computer simulations and real-world processes. We continuously update finite element models (FEM) with real-time data to eliminate uncertainties and enhance precision.

Through **Digital Twinning**, we aim to optimise manufacturing efficiency and address critical industrial challenges, such as controlling sintering shrinkage and distortion, ensuring precision in advanced ceramics and other high-value applications.

Leveraging Machine Learning & Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs):

Improving the accuracy of sintering simulations by replacing empirical laws in finite element analysis with nested ANNs trained with experimental data, enhancing industrial processes like flash sintering.

Predictive Accuracy & Custom Subroutines: By developing custom UMAT, CREEP and MATLAB unites for ABAQUS and COMSOL (using Fortran, Python, and MATLAB), we integrate machine learning and physics-based neural networks, optimizing manufacturing processes and advancing predictive accuracy in critical industrial applications.

Industrial Challenge: Controlling Sintering Shrinkage and Distortion

Digital Twin Lab: Shaping Future Ceramic Manufacturing

Funded for £2.1 million by UKRI's Strength in Places Fund

Impact: Transforming Advanced Ceramics Manufacturing through real-time data integration and digital twin models nested with ANNs, we aim to reduce inefficiencies, lower rejection rates, and minimize post-sintering costs. This approach fine-tunes manufacturing conditions, reducing waste and energy consumption, and promoting sustainable practices.

Collaborative Network: UK Industries and Universities (logos displayed) contribute data, research, and testing environments, ensuring effective integration of digital twins into real-world processes.

Research Expertise of Project Team Members

Prof. Jingzhe Pan
Project PI
Digital twins for manufacturing process of advanced ceramics using finite element analysis with deep machine learning.

Miss Mingxuan Xia
PhD student
Development of nested machine learning algorithm.
Modelling polymer degradation using nested machine learning.

Dr. Ran He
Research fellow
ANNs as constitutive laws in finite element analysis of sintering deformation.
Digital twin of flash sintering using nested machine learning.

Mr. Michael Yu
PhD student
Finite Element Analysis of polyphase flash sintering.
CFD characterisation of 3D-printed ceramic filters.

Mr. Peter Polak
Research fellow
ANNs as viscosities in finite element analysis of sintering deformation.
Digital twin for industrial sintering process using nested machine learning.

Dr. Xiaoxia Yu
Research fellow
Comparative study and documentation of numerical tools used in digital twins of ceramic manufacturing.

Dr. Baber Saleem
Research fellow
Densification based finite element analysis of sintering deformation.
Master sintering curves.
Digital twin for sintering of ceramic matrix composites.

$$\dot{\epsilon}_{ij} = \frac{s_{ij}}{2\eta_s} + \frac{\sigma_m}{3\eta_B} \delta_{ij} - \frac{\sigma_s}{3\eta_B} \delta_{ij}$$